

Thymus vulgaris, a natural pharmacy against COVID-19 and other similar infections: A molecular review

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Abbreviations:

RAS: renin-angiotensin system
ACE: Angiotensin-converting enzyme
ACE2: angiotensin-converting enzyme II
AngII: Angiotensin II
ACEIs: ACE inhibitors
TMPRSS2: transmembrane serine protease 2
AT1R: Angiotensin II receptor type 1
ARBs: angiotensin receptor blockers
TNF: tumor necrosis factor
Th: T helper
IL: Interleukin
CVD: cardio vascular disease
ARDS: acute respiratory distress syndrome
ALI: acute lung injury
BALF: brochalveolar lavage fluid
TGF- β : Transforming growth factor beta

Abstract

A worldwide pandemic infection by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the cause of current deadly disease entitled COVID-19. The virus fuses with the membrane of human host cells via binding of its spike protein to the Angiotensin converting-enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor, leading to an inflammatory-induced tissue damage, especially in the lungs. The renin-angiotensin system (RAS) disturbance, oxidative stress, cytokine storms, and inflammation are the key components in the molecular pathology of COVID-19. This disease can involve the respiratory, cardiovascular, nervous, and digestive systems with deadly consequences. Many attempts have been made to find a solution to treat the disease, but so far no definitive cure has been found. *Thymus vulgaris* L. is a plant with a long history in traditional medicine that has antimicrobial, antiseptic, and antiviral properties. Thymol and Carvacrol are two important biological components in thyme that have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulating properties. NF- κ B, which is down-regulated by thyme, plays a vital role in the regulation of several pro-inflammatory genes. Thyme could suppress TNF- α and IL-6 and other inflammatory cytokines. It also enhances the anti-inflammatory cytokines like TGF- β and IL-10. Thyme extract acts also as an inhibitor of cytokines IL-1-beta and IL-8, at both mRNA and protein levels. Thymol may also reduce the nucleotide-binding domain, leucine-rich-containing family, pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome components, which promote caspase-1-mediated IL-1 β and IL-18 maturation and thus the progression of neuro-inflammation toward neurological disease. Thyme and its active ingredients, especially thymol and carvacrol, have also positive effects on the RAS and intestinal microbiota. Accordingly, *Thymus vulgaris* L and its bioactive components could prevent the COVID-19 side effects and has a potential protective role against the deleterious consequences of the disease.

Keywords: *Thymus vulgaris* L, Thyme, COVID-19, SARS-COV2, infection, treatment

Introduction

A large number of medicinal plant species have been traditionally used in the treatment of several diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, intestinal inflammatory diseases, inflammatory bowel disease, Alzheimer's diseases, and other illnesses (1–3).

Thyme is a plant with a long history in traditional medicine that has antimicrobial, antiseptic, and antiviral properties (3,4). It also has beneficial effects on the respiratory and cardiovascular system (5,6). *Thymus vulgaris* L belongs to the thyme L genus and the Lamiaceae family. This plant is a small and perennial that grows in hot and dry climates (7). The most important compounds in *Thymus vulgaris* L. include thymol, Carvacrol, Linalool, γ -terpinene, p-cymene, β -myrcene, and terpinen-4-ol (5). Some of the health beneficial properties of Thyme are strongly related to its bioactive compounds which include phenols (thymol and carvacrol), phenolic acids (rosmarinic and caffeic acids), and flavonoids (luteolin, quercetin, and apigenin derivatives) (5,6,8,9). This plant is a rich source of vitamins, especially vitamin A, vitamin C, and vitamin B₆. Moreover, in the leaves of this plant, minerals such as potassium, calcium, iron, manganese, magnesium, and selenium are found abundantly (5).

In December 2019, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) spread in Wuhan, China (10). SARS-COV2 is a novel coronavirus, named because of its similar symptoms, biological behavior, and clinical manifestation to the severe acute respiratory syndrome virus (SARS-Cov). SARS-Cov2 causes coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) which as a pandemic infection has so far infected millions of people and hundreds thousands of deaths worldwide (11). The SARS-CoV-2 binds to the ACE2 receptor in human cells through its spike

glycoprotein and enters host cells. As a consequence, this mechanism leads to respiratory infection, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and central neural system involvement(12). The most common clinical characteristics of SARS-COV2 are fever, cough, shortness of breath, muscle pain, confusion, sore throat, rhinorrhea, chest pain, and nausea (13). Although the molecular story of COVID-19 has been greatly identified, no definite treatment has been so far confirmed for the disease. Accordingly, in the current study, the potential therapeutic effects of *Thymus vulgaris* L and its compounds against COVID-19 and other similar viral infections have been molecularly described.

Carvacrol and thymol

Carvacrol [$C_6H_3CH_3(OH)(C_3H_7)$] is a liquid phenolic monoterpenoid which is also named 5-isopropyl- 2-methyl-phenol by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry. This small molecule is the major component in the essential oil of oregano (*Origanum vulgare*), thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), pepperwort (*Lepidium flavum*), and some other plants (14,15). Thymol (2-isopropyl-5-methyl-phenol) also known as “hydroxy cymene” is a colorless crystalline monoterpene phenol that is the main constituent of essential oils derived from the Lamiaceae family, including *Thymus*, *Ocimum* and *Origanum* and other plants belonging to other families like Verbenaceae and Scrophulariaceae (16–18). Similar to carvacrol, Thymol also has a hydroxyl group at a distinct position on the phenolic ring and it is also slightly soluble in water, but soluble in alcohols, alkaline solutions, and other organic solvents (17–19). Thymol exhibits several biological effects such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulating, and free radical scavenging properties. Carvacrol also exhibits antioxidant activities, antimicrobial and anticarcinogenic effects (3,9). Many studies have also demonstrated the effect

of Thymol and Carvacrol on decreasing levels of the proinflammatory cytokines: Interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-6, and tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α (3,6).

The pathophysiology of COVID-19

SARS-CoV2 is an enveloped positive single-stranded RNA virus belonging to beta coronaviruses (11). This virus fuses with the membrane of human respiratory system cells especially type II alveolar cells (AT2) via binding of its spike protein to the ACE2 receptor. It leads to ACE2 cleavage by transmembrane serine protease 2 (TMPRSS2) and causes alveolar damage after infection (20,21). ACE2 is an important molecule in the cellular entry of SARS-CoV-2; So the ACE2 expression in human cells could be an important factor for cell susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 (22). ACE2 is a component of the renin-angiotensin system in the human body that converts angiotensin II (AngII) to angiotensin₍₁₋₇₎ (23), a heptapeptide with various functions, including vasodilation, antifibrotic and antiproliferative effects (24). ACE2 is most commonly expressed in the tissues of the liver, kidneys, and heart (25), whose level is decreased in COVID-19 due to the interaction of virus-ACE2, and as a result, the AngII level increases (26). Angiotensin II is a pre-inflammatory factor whose high level increases oxidative stress and nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) expression. These events could lead to cardiovascular, pulmonary, and renal disorders (27,28). Accordingly, SARS-CoV2 induce acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and acute lung injury (ALI) through the increasing activity of ACE and Ang II by suppressing the expression of ACE2 and decreasing Ang₍₁₋₇₎ (29).

NOX1, a homologous enzyme of NADPH oxidase is expressed in endothelial cells, epithelial cells, smooth muscle cells, and interstitial fibroblasts, while NOX2, another homologous enzyme of NADPH oxidase, is expressed in phagocyte cells, and some organ tissue cells in

cardiovascular, renal, CNS, and GI tracts. The overactivation of AngII in some in pathological conditions, like COVID-19, leads to the upregulation of NOX1 and NOX2 enzymes, the events that result in overproducing the Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) molecules (30,31). Figure1

Thymus vulgaris L. , COVID-19, and renin-angiotensin system

The renin-angiotensin system (RAS) consists of an enzymatic cascade which plays crucial roles in multiple physiological alterations and inflammatory process. Several studies have shown that RAS activation is strictly related to an increase in the inflammatory status, such as inducing the expression of several cytokines, chemokines, and cell adhesion molecules (32–34). There is considerable in-vitro and in-vivo activity of dietary factors regulating RAS elements, but the major focus is on ACE inhibition by a range of dietary peptides from the plant, dairy, and fish (35,36). Glen S et al. showed that among the plants studied, a small selection of plants such as Thyme and Tea have activity in both ACE suppression and inhibition of AngII binding to its receptor (AT1R). They also demonstrated that the ACE inhibitory effect of these herbs is correlated with their polyphenolic component, as demonstrated by other researchers in this field. On the other hand, the correlation between AT1R blocking and these components was non-significant and has been largely associated with the herbal metabolites of several chemical classes. This is suggestive that the herbal components associated with AT1R inhibition activity are likely distinct from those associated with ACE-blockade (35,37). Initial reports recommended that some conditions, including heart disease, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and cardiovascular diseases increase the COVID-19-induced morbidities. Meanwhile, many of those patients are often undertreated with RAS blockers, such as ACE inhibitors (ACEIs) or angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) (38,39). Nevertheless, the therapeutic potential of

ACEIs/ARBs drugs in COVID-19 is controversial. As the ACE2 receptor facilitates SARS-CoV-2 to invade target cells, SARS-CoV-2 binding to ACE2 reduces ACE2 expression some (26). studies have shown that in patients undertreated with ACEIs/ARBs, the expression of ACE2 is elevated. Accordingly, some experts speculated that treatment with ACEIs/ARBs could potentially enhance infection with COVID-19 (38,40). There is, however, no evidence to confirm the notion that ACEIs/ARBs can facilitate coronavirus entry by increasing ACE2 expression (39). On the other hand, some other studies have illustrated that in COVID-19 patients, serum AngII level is higher than healthy people which can upregulate the expression of inflammatory cytokines through the activation of AT1R (38,41). Therefore, the usage of ACEIs/ARBs such as Thyme could be beneficial for COVID-19 patients.

The Anti-inflammatory effects of *Thymus vulgaris* L. in COVID-19

In SARS-CoV-2 infection, the level of AngII increases (26). The binding of AngII to AngII type 1 receptor (AT1R) is a crucial mediator for most of the pro-inflammatory effects. The AngII type 2 receptor (AT2R) is activated by AngII which leads to the activation of some inflammatory cells. AT1R activation induces the overexpression of adhesion molecules, chemokines, and cytokines via different pathways such as NF-kB up-regulation. NF-kB plays a vital role in the regulation of several pro-inflammatory genes (32,42,43). As previously described, thyme also acts as a negative regulator of NF-kB (44). Moreover, other studies showed that the plasma levels of most pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL1B, IL1RA, IL7, IL8, IL9, IL10, TNF, basic fibroblast growth factor (FGF), and other pro-inflammatory factors were increased in COVID-19(45,46). Therefore, according to the studies that have shown Thyme as an inhibitory

agent of pro-inflammatory cytokines (6,8,47), *Thymus vulgaris* L. can be considered in the therapeutic approach of the patients with COVID-19. Figure2

The potential therapeutic effects of *Thymus vulgaris* L. for Respiratory problems in COVID-19

Compounds such as thymol and carvacrol found in thyme are traditionally used to treat chronic bronchitis, cough, sore throat, colds, asthma, and other respiratory infections. Thyme is an antiseptic, expectorant, and antispasmodic herbal medicine with respiratory clearance characteristics (48–50). As mentioned, acute lung injury (ALI) and its severest form, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) are the main reason for COVID-19 mortality. Damage of endothelial and epithelial respiratory cells, neutrophil infiltration, an extended-release of pro-inflammatory mediators, and pulmonary edema and inflammation are characteristics of ARDS (51–53). Severe COVID-19 patients represent cytokine storm characteristics. In cytokine storm, the serum levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-8, IL-17, and TNF- α elevate (54). Cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 recruit neutrophils and other inflammatory cells into the lung and increase their response to activators. Cytokine release leads to respiratory endothelial dysfunction which results in microvascular permeability and protein leakage followed by hypoxemia (55,56). TNF- α and IL-6 are components of an inflammatory response and have been shown to induce the occurrence of ARDS/ALI (57). Wan et al. indicated the immunomodulatory effect of thymol in lipopolysaccharide-induced ARDS through TNF- α and IL-6 suppression in the broncho-alveolar lavage fluid (BALF) (44).

NF- κ B, a protein complex that triggers a pro-inflammatory signaling pathway in the lung leading to cytokine release is overexpressed in ALI and ARDS (58). NF- κ B pathway is activated through

two distinct ways: the canonical and non-canonical pathways. p65 and p50 are members of the canonical pathway triggered by pro-inflammatory cytokines (as IL-1). On the other hand, p52 and RelB are members of the non-canonical pathway and they are associated with the normal lymphoid organ development. Studies have shown that the thyme extract is a negative regulator of NF- κ B p65 and NF- κ B p52 transcription factors whereby pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 beta and IL-8) are reduced. Studies also demonstrated that the thyme extract acts as an inhibitor of cytokines IL-1-beta and IL-8, at both mRNA and protein levels in normal human epithelial cells (8,59,60). Thymol can also decrease the recruitment of inflammatory cells like neutrophils into BALF. Thymol inhibits NF- κ B activation (44) which is a transcription regulator of inflammatory and immune response genes (61); an event that can decrease the severity of ALI/ARDS.

Carvacrol, another active constituent of thyme has been also shown to have a therapeutic effect on ALI/ARSD. The remedial effect of carvacrol on ARDS is through decreasing the inflammatory cytokines, reducing the number of inflammatory cells in BALF, and inhibition of NF- κ B (62). As a result, thyme can be effective in improving the respiratory symptoms of COVID-19 patients.

The Cardio-protective effects of *Thymus vulgaris* L. in COVID-19

Thyme has been used as a remedy for hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases in traditional medicine from ancient. Thyme has effective components such as thymol and carvacrol against oxidative agents causing cardiovascular disease (63). Cardiovascular damages are prevalent morbidity in COVID-19 patients. Meanwhile, patients with cardiovascular disease (CVDs) are more susceptible to have severe COVID-19 symptoms, especially acute myocardial

injury (64,65). SARS-COV2 might induce myocardial injury through the cytokine storm associated with a severe response by type 1 and type 2 T helper cells. Moreover, COVID-19-induced hypoxemia and respiratory failure could lead to myocardial dysfunction (66). Cytokine storms could induce multiple organ failure and increase inflammatory chemokines such as IL-6, IL-2, IL-7, interferon- γ , (TNF)- α . It shows that cardiovascular injury correlates with elevated inflammatory markers (67). Moreover, the oxidative stress generated by SARS-CoV-2 could cause heart damage (68). *Thymus vulgaris* L. contains antioxidant components, and studies show that a proper dose of antioxidants can improve the heart damage caused by COVID-19 infection (5,68). It has been also demonstrated in many studies that thymol and carvacrol, derivatives of *T. vulgaris*, have anti-inflammatory effects (3,69,70). So it seems *T. vulgaris* and its derivatives can protect cardiovascular damages induced by SARS-COV2.

The Neuroprotective effects of *Thymus vulgaris* L. in COVID-19

Some COVID-19 patients have neurologic symptoms such as dizziness, headache, hypogeusia and hyposmia and vomiting (71). These symptoms are suggestive for neuroinvasive potencies of the virus (72). Past studies on SARS-CoV revealed that it could reach CNS through the bloodstream or olfactory bulb neuronal circuits. Moreover, ACE2, the receptor of SARS-CoV2, is expressed in astroglial cells and neurons in different regions of the CNS (73). Interaction of ACE2 with SARS-CoV2 spike protein leads to an increase in the AngII/Ang₍₁₋₇₎ ratio, which is the main reason for cytokine storm in patients (26). Other studies represent that increasing the secretion of some inflammatory molecules like IL-6, IL-12, IL-15, and TNF- α in CoV-infected glial cells can have an immunopathological role in inflamed brains (73,74).

Otherwise, thymol and carvacrol, the bioactive molecules isolated from *Thymus vulgaris*, could down-regulate the activation of NF- κ B signaling in lipopolysaccharide-treated macrophages (75). Besides, the level of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α was decreased in mice hippocampus by using thymol (76). *Thymus vulgaris* L. also enhances the anti-inflammatory cytokines like TGF- β and IL-10 which reduce the release of inflammatory cytokines by astrocytes (77). Thymol may also reduce the nucleotide-binding domain, leucine-rich-containing family, pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome components, which promote caspase-1-mediated interleukin-1 β and interleukin-18 maturation in microglia and thus the progression of neuro-inflammation toward neurological disease (78). Altogether, *Thymus vulgaris* can inhibit the pathogenic pathway of the virus through some anti-inflammatory potencies that counteract the destructive effects of SARS-CoV2 on the brains of the patients.

Gut microbiota, COVID-19, and *Thymus vulgaris* L.

The intestinal microbiota is a vast collection of microorganisms in the human gastrointestinal tract that play a determinant role in disease and health (79). Dysbiosis, an imbalance in human microbiota, can lead to some respiratory problems, such as asthma, COPD (Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease), and CF (Cystic fibrosis) (80). In patients with respiratory disorders such as COVID-19, the association between the lungs and the intestines leads to gut disturbance. Thus, improving the gut microbiota can be considered to the therapeutic approach of the COVID-19 patients (81). An experimental study indicated that the thyme extract can improve the gut microbial population (82). The mixture of virgin olive oil and thyme phenolic compounds could increase the populations of bifidobacteria in another study. So a mixture of virgin olive oil and thyme phenolic compounds have prebiotic properties (83). More detailed studies should be

performed to better describe the effect of thyme on the intestinal microbiota (84). However, it seems *Thymus vulgaris* L. can be effective on the treatment of the patients with COVID-19 through improving the gut microbiota. Figure1,2

Conclusion

SARS-CoV-2 is an agent of COVID-19 disease, which is pandemic in the world. This virus by increasing oxidative stress, inflammation, and disturbance in RAS, leads to damage in the body organs, especially the respiratory and the cardiovascular system. *Thymus vulgaris* L. and its bioactive components such as Thymol and Carvacrol suppress the negative effects of the renin-angiotensin system in COVID-19 patients. Moreover, it decreases pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and TNF- α . So it can decrease the severity of ALI/ARDS. *Thymus vulgaris* reduces the oxidative stress due to its antioxidant properties that can reduce cardiovascular adverse in COVID-19 infection. Meanwhile, it has neuroprotective effects by enhancing the anti-inflammatory cytokines like TGF- β and Inhibition of inflammatory pathways. Finally, we can conclude thyme has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulating properties and reduce side effects in COVID-19 patients.

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Figures

Figure 1. An infographic picture illustrating the molecular pathway of SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis and also the molecular pathway of Thymus Vulgaris L. potencies against COVID-19. (ANG: Angiotensin)

(a). This virus causes body organ damage by increasing oxidative stress, inflammation, and disturbance in RAS. (ACE: Angiotensin-converting enzyme)

(b). Thyme affects the renin-angiotensin system by both ACE suppression and inhibition of AngII binding to its receptor (AT1R: Angiotensin II receptor type 1).

(c). NF-kB, which is down-regulated by thyme, plays a vital role in the regulation of several pro-inflammatory genes.

(d). Increased cytokines (IL-6, IL-2, IL-7, interferon- γ , TNF- α), oxidative stress, and hypoxemia, which are induced by SARS-CoV-2, lead to myocardial injury. On the other hand, thymus Vulgaris contains antioxidant and anti-inflammatory components which can improve the heart damage caused by COVID-19 infection.

(e). Cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 recruit inflammatory cells into the lung and increase their response to activators. Cytokine storm leads to respiratory endothelial dysfunction which results in microvascular permeability and protein leakage followed by hypoxemia. Otherwise, thyme suppresses TNF- α and IL-6.

(f). Thyme decreases the level of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α and downregulates the activation of NF-Kb. It also enhances the anti-inflammatory cytokines like TGF- β and IL-10, reducing the release of inflammatory cytokines.

(g). Some inflammatory molecules like IL-6, IL-12, IL-15, and TNF- α may have an immunopathological role in infected brains. Otherwise, Thyme extract acts as an inhibitor of cytokines IL-1-beta and IL-8, at both mRNA and protein levels.

(h). Thymol may also reduce the nucleotide-binding domain, leucine-rich-containing family, pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome components, which promote caspase-1-mediated interleukin-1 β and interleukin-18 maturation and thus the progression of neuro-inflammation toward neurological disease.

Figure 2. An infographic diagram illustrating the potential therapeutic effects of Thymus Vulgaris L. in COVID-19.

ACE: Angiotensin-converting enzyme

AngII: Angiotensin II

AT1R: Angiotensin II receptor type 1

TNF: tumor necrosis factor

IL: Interleukin

TGF- β : Transforming growth factor-beta

NLRP3: nucleotide-binding domain, leucine-rich-containing family, pyrin domain-containing 3